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EXPLORING EDUCATION THROUGH THE EYES OF SCIENCE

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Students usually think that they cannot use all their learnings in school in real life. They thought that Equation in Math is useless but actually, it's a form of practicing their critical and logical thinking, proving their view points and make decisions on what they actually want to justify. Science concepts are the one that helps environment to progress, develop, and grow, but for students it's useless and did not see the big picture of it in the near future.

Today's current issue is a big problem to all of us. Big adjustments happened and transition is roughly made. In this matter, we can ask help from Science. Increasingly, development of science had made a huge help on how we currently survived Covid-19 pandemic. Data gathering, electronic devices, fast communication, and disseminating information are examples of progress of Science. This is very important for us, especially in this time of crisis, that we are using this Sciences to prevail the pandemic. By using it, everything is smoothly happening, on temperature testing, vaccines, hospital electronic devices, and especially communication. Human and non-human existence were altered as a result of these development and actions.

We should expand science in the modern education, for this will succour basic and hard problems that everyone may encounter. Many of these issues are intertwined with scientific and technological endeavors. Students must take this subjects seriously from basic unit of life to saving future's life. It should focus more to a realistic situation and scenario, which is advancement to technologically and scientifically devices to produce some high quality products that tend to help face different environmental problems. Moreover, the heavy emphasis on researches puts the cutting edge of changes in knowledge, and in values as well.

Science Education is compacted with social and natural science that are designed to promote future generations' awareness and participation on global concerns while also addressing the social elements of these issues. Science's vital role is to develop global changes, not only in human but also to non-human. New generations are fully equipped with knowledge in growing diversity and equity in science that give importance in progress globally.

In globalization, it is not simply the ties of economic and political exchange but also the shared knowledge, awareness, and consciousness. That awareness leads to a bigger picture of movements of people and an array of different sciences to have formal education on current situation. Despite of the increase of modern sciences, it has also advancement in challenges that threaten the environment, examples of these are Covid and Delta Variant.

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For this such, Science must link in these issues and focus more on the competencies that help solve social and environmental problems. Quality education must have emphasize more on all aspects and disciplines to enhance more future researchers, scientists, and professionals. The role of education is to help the society to work out social issues and problems with the help of nature of Science. More comprehensive data gathering and researches must teach students in order for them to explore things. Teachers should tell students who study Science that they may help future's conflict, that they can be the answer, they can be future's solution.

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